

Assessing different hydroponic subsystems for Batavia lettuce growth under different planting density treatments

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Abstract

Hydroponic systems have the potential for being one of the most promising sustainable alternative methods of food production, where they confer the advantages of producing higher yields with better control over plant growth. The main purpose of this study is to determine differences in growth rates, sensory attributes and nutrient uptake upon growing lettuce (*Lactuca sativa* L.) in various hydroponic subsystems at two different plant spacings. We investigated the interaction of different effects on lettuce growth in four hydroponic subsystems, Deep Water Culture (DWC), Nutrient Film Technique (NFT), Media-Bed system (MB) and Sandponic (SP), at two different plant densities, at narrow planting spacings (20 x 25 cm), and larger planting spacings (24 x 25 cm). Our findings show that cultivation methods and planting spacing greatly influence lettuce growth. Overall, the present study provides direct evidence that DWC and NFTs subsystems at both planting spacings performed the best in terms of giving higher yield production, higher plant growth parameters, and better sensory attributes compared to other cultivation systems. Lettuces grown in the DWC system had higher chlorophyll B (29.13 ± 0.82 mg/100 g), and carotene content (32.40 ± 1.27 mg/100 g) in narrow planting spacing and were the most preferred lettuces according to taste tests (52.4%).

1 Introduction

Current agricultural production systems face unprecedented challenges towards becoming reliably robust, competitive and environmentally sustainable food production systems, due to a number of existing and emerging reasons, such as soil surface infertility, soil degradation, unfavourable soil compaction, the prevalence of soil-borne disease agents, nematodes in soil, outbreaks of crop pests, weed infestation, overuse and misuse of pesticides, monoculture approach, and drought stress¹⁻⁴. The fertile soils become unsuitable for agricultural production due to the long-term use of synthetic fertilizers, environmental pollution and urbanization phenomena^{2,5}. Poor nutrient uptake by plants from infertile soils can be insufficient for plant growth and consequently, needs land reclamation processes to make the soil healthy again⁶. On the one hand, climate change causes droughts leading to a decline in surface and groundwater resources. Moreover, climate change as a driver leads to an increase in the rate of drylands and agricultural drought. As the agriculture sector is highly dependent on water availability where agricultural irrigation accounts for the majority of world water use by 70%, agricultural food production is increasingly subject to water scarcity risk⁷⁻¹¹. Moreover, most of the on-farm irrigation systems are low efficient coupled with poor irrigation practice¹²⁻¹⁴. Under the projected increase in water shortage and non-arable land, the development of controlled sustainable farming techniques such as hydroponics, provide an alternative and sustainable food production that is efficient on water use yet guarantees higher crop yield compared to conventional farming techniques^{15,16}.

Hydroponics is a soilless plant cultivation technique, in which plant roots are submersed in nutrition solution with or without the use of an inert medium such as gravel, sand, perlite and other substrates to provide mechanical support^{17,18}. A nutrition solution for hydroponics contains certain essential elements, mainly inorganic ions from soluble salts for optimal plant growth¹⁹. From the perspective of agronomists, there are a number of differences between hydroponically and soil-grown plants in terms of nutrient uptake. In both cultivation systems, inorganic and organic matters must be broken down and dissolved in water so that plants can absorb the nutrients. In soil cultivation, nutrient elements stick to soil particles and are then passed into the soil solution (i.e. the liquid phase of soil which consists of dissolved organic and inorganic substances and are responsible for the transport of nutrients), whereas in hydroponic systems, nutrient elements from the nutrition solution have direct contact with plant roots by which minerals and water are immediately available and uptake by the plants¹⁷. In soil cultivation, crops compete with weeds for nutrient uptake, light or space (interspecific competition), while crop production can be reduced by biotic stressors such as weeds, soilless agri-tech cultivation methods do not require a mechanical workforce for weed control²⁰. Another important parameter is plant density, which mainly affects plant yield and crop quality in soil cultivation, where plants compete for limited resources such as water and soil nutrients (intraspecific competition). This competition influences plant development more than the interspecific competition for the similarity in resource requirements between the same species^{21,22}. An optimal plant density should be determined based on maintaining a balance between the effective use of resources, and the production of high crop yields, where inter- or intra-specific competition should be kept at a minimum. Furthermore, due to climatic and cultivar differences, optimal plant spacing may depend on the season and cultivar. Economically feasible hydroponic cultivation requires selecting the optimal plant density as well as an optimal subsystem as hydroponic components due to high initial investment costs²³⁻²⁶.

Within hydroponics, several techniques allow for the optimal customization of a plant growing operation, which is principally similar but has some functional differences. Commonly used hydroponic subsystems are (deep) water culture system (DWC), nutrient film technique (NFT) and media-bed systems which use substrates such as gravel, sand, and rock wool^{27,28}.

Hydroponic cultivation techniques are gaining popularity because of their efficient management of water and nutrients. Various crops can be grown using hydroponics including leafy vegetables, tomatoes etc. Lettuce is one of the leafy greens that can be successfully and easily grown in hydroponic systems. This leafy culture plant is a cool-season vegetable which requires growth temperatures ranging from 7 to 24°C, with an average of 18°C^{18,23}. Here, we tested the lettuce growth and yield interaction between different subsystems of hydroponics and different planting densities. We hypothesized that the leaf yield of lettuces per unit area increases with increased plant density, while leaf yield per plant decreases with increasing plant density. In detail, we aimed at determining the effects of different subsystems and planting densities on vegetative growth, sensory attributes and nutrient uptake by lettuce grown in a closed soilless system.

2 Materials and Methods

2.1 Pre- experimental procedure

Lettuce seeds (*Lactuca sativa* L., cv. *Batavia* F1) produced by Rijk Zwaan were purchased from the local distributor in Egypt. Seeds of *Batavia* lettuces sown at 1–2 cm depth into trays (70 x 40 cm), 209 cells. The mixture of 70% peat moss, 15% vermiculite, and 15% perlite was used for the seedlings as growing media. At the time of media preparation, 8.5 g of (N-P-K, 19.19.19 + T.E) fertilizer was added to the growing media for 1 complete seedling tray (209 cells) and

was irrigated. Once the cotyledons were fully expanded and the first true leaves began to emerge, the seedlings were sprayed with a dose of 0.5 g of NPK (19/19/19 + TE (Trace Elements)) fertilizer per 1 L of water with 3-day intervals. The pH and EC of the growing media were measured daily and maintained within a range of 5.4 to 6.0 and 1.5–2.0 dS/m, respectively. In the summer season, seedlings were irrigated 2 times a day, once with water only and once with the nutrient spray at around 6–7 am and 5–7 pm. After seedlings reached a growth stage of 5–7 leaves, along with root development, they were spread properly in the planter, and 23 ± 2-day-old seedlings were transplanted into the grow beds.

2.2 Experimental design and system setup

These experiments were designed to compare the four hydroponic growing sub-systems and different planting spacings. Moreover, all results in hydroponic experiments were compared with soil-grown lettuces. Two identical treatments were performed in August and September 2021 under greenhouse conditions in Cairo, Egypt (30°2'41" N, 31°14'44" E, altitude 26 masl). The research greenhouse's dimensions were 30 m L x 6 m W x 2.85m H. A completely randomized experimental design was conducted with two planting spacing treatments in triplicates, that is, the experimental system with three lettuce grow beds as for each hydroponic subsystem. As Fig. 1 shows, Deep Water Culture (DWC), Nutrient Film Technique (NFT), Media-bed system (MB) and Sandponic (SP) are hydroponic sub-systems, in which experimental lettuce plants were grown, and their performance was tested for optimal lettuce growth. The area of the hydroponic experimental unit was 1.92 m² for each replicate. The planting area in soil-based cultivation was 4 m² for each unit. Planting spacings were 20x25 cm (90 lettuces), and 24x25 cm (at least 72 plants) for hydroponic subsystems. Hydroponically grown plants were supplied with full-strength Hoagland's nutrient solution (containing N 210 mg/L, K 235 mg/L, Ca 200 mg/L, P 31 mg/L, S 64 mg/L, Mg 48 mg/L, B 0.5 mg/L, Fe 1 to 5 mg/L, Mn 0.5 mg/L, Zn 0.05 mg/L, Cu 0.02 mg/L, Mo 0.01 mg/L)²⁹. Each hydroponic sub-system had a 500 L total volume of nutritious water in the whole system. 324 L of water filled in the grow beds of DWC units, and the water depth in the grow bed was 17 cm. In the DWC system, plants were supported by a styrofoam board which floats on a bath of nutrient solution. The styrofoam board has holes for the plants, which allows the roots to be submerged in the water and have constant contact with the nutrient solution. Aeration was supplied via diffuser air-stone to the root zone of plants, which was placed under a raft and connected to an air pump (280 W), which constantly pumps air to ensure high oxygen concentrations in the water of the grow beds. DWC and NFT systems worked with a continuous flow technique with a cycle of 7 L/min of pumping for 10 min and then 51 seconds off. In DWC, water was pumped with a submersible pump at a rate of 50 min per hour, whereas water in the NFT system was pumped at a rate of 55 min per hour. The NFT system was designed using pipes. The highly oxygenated dissolved nutrient solution was recirculated continuously to the roots of lettuce plants through a set of channels, the solution ran off into the nutrient tank and was pumped back to the plants. The reservoir contained a submersible pump and air stones for optimal dissolved oxygen levels for optimal nutrient uptake. Plants were placed in plastic cups hung in pipes to support the plants, so they do not fall over during continuous streams of water.

The sand was prepared for use by washing to remove salt composition in SP systems, whereas gravel was used in MB systems as growth media for supporting plants. In SP and soil cultivation (SC), irrigation was performed with drip irrigation and drainage (surface drainage in Sandponics, deep infusion drainage system in soil cultivation). MB worked with continuous flow technique and drainage (a bell siphon system). Water was pumped with a capacity of 7 L/min for 2 min and was then turned off for 2 h and with a capacity of 7 L/min pumps water was pumped for 10 min and was then turned off for 2 min in Sandponic and Media-bed system, respectively (irrigation rate per hour was 1 min in SP and 50 min in MB).

The environmental parameters such as air temperature, relative humidity, and CO₂ were daily measured and collected using an online data logger (Tomatiki Smart Data Logger, Model: SDL320). The greenhouse was covered with polyethylene plastic and with a pad and fan evaporative cooling system. Desired climate set points were maintained by an automatic climate control system. The shading net (73% shading rate) is used on long summer days to reduce solar radiation. Table 1 summarizes the environmental conditions for lettuces in growing beds and in the closed greenhouse for experiments. The pH of the solution was maintained at a range of 5.5–6.5 with the addition of a base, potassium hydroxide (KOH) and nitric acid when it gets too high³⁰. The electrical conductivity (EC) is a measure of the dissolved salts in a solution, which is another important factor for nutrient uptake in hydroponic systems, and EC value is maintained between 1.5 and 2.0 dS m⁻¹ in hydroponic systems³¹. Benoit and Ceustermans (1987, 1988)^{32,33} have found the EC of Hoagland solution to be 2.2 dS m⁻¹ and recommended maintaining the EC range between (2.0–2.5 dS m⁻¹) in their studies for hydroponics. Therefore, the EC range could be kept in between a large range (1.5–2.5 dS m⁻¹) in experimental setups based on these two recommendations. When the EC value increased, it was diluted by adding water. Matured hydroponically grown lettuces were harvested on the 28th and 29th DAT over 2 days.

Table 1
The environmental conditions for lettuces in growing beds and closed greenhouse in the trial 1 and 2

Treatments	CS	pH	EC (µS/cm)	DO (mg/L)	Water T (°C)	Air T (°C)	CO ₂ (ppm)	Air RH
Narrow spacing 20x25 cm	DWC	5.65 ± 0.56	1.55 ± 0.03	5.16 ± 0.43	27.39 ± 0.67	28.38 ± 1.49	1759.21 ± 802.19	67.80 ± 4.39
	NFT	5.74 ± 0.26	1.57 ± 0.05	5.17 ± 0.37	27.59 ± 1.34	28.38 ± 1.49	1759.21 ± 802.19	67.80 ± 4.39
	MB	6.36 ± 0.32	1.74 ± 0.14	5.4 ± 0.37	27.1 ± 0.5	28.38 ± 1.49	1759.21 ± 802.19	67.80 ± 4.39
	SP	6.51 ± 0.32	2.18 ± 0.24	4.25 ± 0.63	27.07 ± 1.1	28.38 ± 1.49	1759.21 ± 802.19	67.80 ± 4.39
Larger spacing 24x25 cm	DWC	5.69 ± 0.47	1.52 ± 0.07	5.21 ± 0.3	26.46 ± 0.74	26.55 ± 1.19	1906.32 ± 694.63	70.22 ± 3.29
	NFT	5.7 ± 0.46	1.55 ± 0.05	5.11 ± 0.62	26.81 ± 0.87	26.55 ± 1.19	1906.32 ± 694.63	70.22 ± 3.29
	MB	6.13 ± 0.35	1.82 ± 0.11	5.48 ± 0.31	26.14 ± 0.76	26.55 ± 1.19	1906.32 ± 694.63	70.22 ± 3.29
	SP	6.5 ± 0.19	1.98 ± 0.15	3.6 ± 0.56	26.25 ± 1.3	26.55 ± 1.19	1906.32 ± 694.63	70.22 ± 3.29

Parameters: EC: electrical conductivity, DO: Dissolved oxygen, CO₂: Carbon dioxide. CS: cultivation systems: DWC: Deep water culture, NFT: Nutrient Film Technique, MB: Media- bed system and SP: Sandponic.

2.3 Growth Parameter Measurements

The height of leaves, fresh shoot mass, fresh root mass, total number of leaves, stem diameter, head diameter and leaf number per plant were measured on-site at the harvesting time of the lettuces. Generally, a representative sample of 10 plants per replicate was taken. Before starting measurements, substrates in the roots of the plants were removed and plants were gently washed off. Then, the surface moisture on the lettuce was removed using a soft paper towel. Plant heights were measured from the base of the shoot to the terminal growing point. The root length of the lettuces was measured from the base of the shoot to the tip of the main root on the lettuces. The root and shoot weights of all lettuces were weighed. Lettuce head diameters were measured from the top of the lettuces and recorded in two orthogonal directions. The lettuce was divided into two parts from the base of the shoot and the diameters of the stems on the lettuce were measured. The total number of leaves was obtained by counting the number of fully expanded healthy leaves per plant and averages determined in 10 samples from each growth unit.

2.4 Leaf Content Analysis

18 lettuce leaves in each sub-treatment were randomly taken from each cultivation system for nutrient content analysis on 26 ± 2 DAT. Nutrient content analysis and measurement of dry mass were performed at the Agricultural Research Center, Giza, Egypt. Nitrogen (N) content was determined using the Micro-Kjeldahl method in the digested solution as described by Plummer (1978)³⁴. The digestive solution (5ml) was distilled with (10ml) of sodium hydroxide (NaOH) for 10 minutes to obtain ammonia. Phosphorus (P) was determined colourimetrically according to the procedures described by Jackson (1958)³⁵. Potassium (K), calcium (Ca), and sodium (Na) contents were determined against a standard using a flame-photometer (JEN way flame photometer) as described by Piper (1950)³⁶. Magnesium (Mg), copper (Cu), manganese (Mn), zinc (Zn) and Iron (Fe) contents were determined by using atomic absorption spectrophotometer, Pyeunican SP1900, according to methods of Brandifeld and Spincer (1965)³⁷. The contents of chlorophyll and carotenoids were determined spectrophotometrically according to the acetone method described by Ritchie (2006)³⁸.

2.5 Taste tests

Immediately after harvest, lettuces were rinsed in water and cut into small-sized pieces and stored at 5°C in plastic boxes, and placed in the fridge overnight. Consumer perception tests were conducted on the following day on-site. Lettuce taste was examined by a minimum of 20 tasters. Lettuces were served to tasters with blinding codes in random order. Taste scores for each cultivation method were obtained by taking weighted averages of taste and smell tests. Testers answered demographic questions such as gender and age to determine whether age and gender affect the taste perception of lettuces. A 10-point hedonic scale (1 = extremely dislike; 10 = extremely like, 5 = none detected) was used to evaluate the overall appearance, overall flavour, aftertaste and crunchiness of lettuces (1–10), a 5-point hedonic scale (1 = not at all bitter or sweet; 5 = extremely bitter or sweet) was used to evaluate the sweetness and bitterness of lettuces grown in different cultivation methods. In addition, the colour of the lettuces was evaluated with this 5-point hedonic scale (1 = extremely dislike, 5 = extremely like). Moreover, lettuce smells and preference for best lettuces were evaluated by testers.

2.6 Statistical analysis

Data are presented as means \pm SE. ANOVA (two-way ANOVA) was performed to detect significant differences in all the measured parameters after verifying homoscedasticity by Levene's test. LSD test was used to compare means at $P = 0.05$. All statistical analyses were conducted using SPSS Statistics 29 (IBM Software, Chicago, USA). Probabilities of significance among treatments and LSD ($P \leq 0.05$) were used to compare means among treatments.

3 Results

3.1 Vegetative Grow Parameters

The hydroponic subsystems and planting spacing as the main effect affected shoot height ($P < 0.001$). In both planting spacing treatments, the average shoot height of the lettuces harvested from the DWC growth bed was significantly higher than the average measured in lettuces from other cultivation methods, whereas the lowest shoot heights were observed in lettuce grown in MB and SP (Table 2). The average fresh weight of the harvested shoots was affected significantly by interactions between treatments and cultivation methods ($F(3, 88) = 12.84, P < 0.001$). Planting spacing was not significant for lettuce shoot weight ($P > 0.05$). The highest fresh shoot masses were measured in lettuce grown in DWC and NFT for both planting spacings. Another important parameter is the stem diameter, which was affected by interactions between cultivation methods and plant density treatments ($F(3, 88) = 6.33, P < 0.001$). The smallest stem diameter was measured in lettuces grown in the SP system among soilless systems for both planting density, whereas stem diameters of lettuces grown in NFT and DWC were higher than in other cultivation methods. For the head diameter of lettuces, the difference between interactions of hydroponic subsystems and planting spacing was significant ($F(3, 88) = 3.80, P = 0.01$). The head diameter as one of the growth parameters was higher in lettuces grown in DWC and NFT systems than in those of other hydroponic systems. Another component of the growth parameter is the number of leaves in lettuce. The hydroponic subsystem as the main effect has also significantly affected the number of leaves in lettuce ($P < 0.001$). The number of leaves was higher in DWC and NFT systems than in MB and SP in the treatment with narrow planting spacing, whereas the number of leaves in lettuce grown in the MB grow beds was not significantly greater than in DWC and NFT with wider planting spacing. The lowest number of lettuce leaves was found in SP. The root length of lettuces was affected significantly by interactions between treatments and cultivation methods ($F(12, 220) = 22.24, P < 0.001$). The interaction between hydroponic subsystems and planting spacings affected the root length of lettuces ($F(3, 88) = 12.25, P < 0.001$). The highest root length was measured at 39.19 cm in lettuces grown with narrow planting spacing in the NFT system, whereas the highest measurement was in lettuce roots from the DWC system with larger spacing. The root length of lettuce in Sandponic systems was significantly shorter than those measured from either DWC, NFT, or MB systems. The difference between the tested hydroponic systems was found significant in terms of the interaction between plant density and cultivation method upon measuring lettuce root weights ($F(3, 88) = 22.20, P < 0.001$); where the average root weight of harvested lettuces from the NFT system with the narrow planting spacing

treatment was higher than those observed in other cultivation systems, while the lowest root weight was in lettuces grown in the SP system for both plant density treatments.

Table 2
Vegetative growth parameters

Treatments	Cultivation systems	Shoot height (cm)	Shoot fresh mass (g)	stem diameter (cm)	Head diameter (cm)	Number of leaves (n)	root length (cm)	Root weight (g)
Narrow spacing 20x25 cm	DWC	17.38 ± 0.72 ^a	160.63 ± 37.01 ^a	1.16 ± 0.12 ^b	25.35 ± 1.48 ^a	34.14 ± 6.61 ^a	33.93 ± 6.55 ^b	27.89 ± 2.55 ^b
	NFT	16.23 ± 0.47 ^b	165.28 ± 25.14 ^a	1.37 ± 0.14 ^a	25.71 ± 1.23 ^a	34.39 ± 3.81 ^a	39.19 ± 5.72 ^a	52.34 ± 11.72 ^a
	MB	15.12 ± 1.32 ^c	100.94 ± 9.54 ^b	1.09 ± 0.14 ^b	21.78 ± 0.9 ^b	27.25 ± 4.33 ^b	21.79 ± 3.86 ^c	20.91 ± 2.42 ^c
	SP	14.36 ± 0.87 ^c	78.61 ± 14.76 ^b	0.93 ± 0.12 ^c	19.33 ± 1.33 ^c	22.86 ± 5.53 ^b	10.68 ± 1.19 ^d	11.14 ± 4.18 ^d
larger spacing 24x25 cm	DWC	16.59 ± 1.25 ^a	204.64 ± 24.77 ^a	1.31 ± 0.19 ^a	23.82 ± 1.74 ^a	35.61 ± 2.72 ^a	28.92 ± 6.02 ^a	32.36 ± 4.57 ^a
	NFT	15.56 ± 1.18 ^a	189.28 ± 19.93 ^a	1.19 ± 0.13 ^a	22.36 ± 1.64 ^a	35.82 ± 3.58 ^a	26.13 ± 4.50 ^{ab}	32.11 ± 6.10 ^a
	MB	13.38 ± 0.68 ^b	87.17 ± 23.23 ^b	1.04 ± 0.08 ^b	19.09 ± 1.07 ^b	32.05 ± 5.60 ^a	22.35 ± 2.64 ^b	22.18 ± 6.45 ^b
	SP	12.49 ± 0.59 ^b	51.29 ± 14.45 ^c	0.92 ± 0.11 ^b	15.27 ± 1.17 ^c	25.27 ± 4.50 ^b	10.73 ± 1.11 ^c	10.70 ± 1.88 ^c

Data are expressed as means ± standard error (SE). Lower case letters within each main treatment indicate significant differences after least significant difference (LSD) post hoc test (significance level $p < 0.05$ and $p < 0.01$, not significantly at $p \geq 0.05$) for each parameter. DWC: Deep water culture, NFT: Nutrient Film Technique, MB: Media- bed system, and SP: Sandponic.

3.2 Leaf Nutrient Composition, Chlorophyll and Carotene Contents

Except for N, Mn, Fe and Cu, B and Mo, the leaf content of each nutrient differed significantly between cultivation systems ($P < 0.05$) (Table 3). The phosphorus (P) content was significantly higher in the lettuces grown in the NFT subsystem with narrow spacing, whereas Potassium (K) content was observed to be less in lettuce leaves from the NFT set-up among the cultivation methods with larger planting spacing. Sodium (Na) content was significantly higher for lettuces from the Sandponic setup compared to other hydroponically grown lettuces. Calcium (Ca) content for MB and SP was higher than in other cultivation methods. The amount of magnesium was much higher in the wider planting spacing setup than in the narrow planting spacing. While no significant statistical difference was there between different cultivation methods for the magnesium content in the first treatment, the magnesium content was the highest in the lettuce grown in the MB system in the wider planting setup compared to others. Zink (Zn) content was significantly higher in SP among cultivation systems with high planting density, whereas it was the lowest for lettuces in the NFT system.

Table 3

The leaf nutrient compositions are indicated as percentage from dry mass, and for macro-elements and Na content, and microelements as and mg/100g

Treatments	CS	N %	P %	K %	Na %	Ca %	Mg mg/100g	Mn mg/100g	Zn mg/100g	Fe mg/100g	Cu mg/100g	B mg/100g	Mo mg/100g
T1.1	DWC	1.91 ± 0.27 ^a	0.93 ± 0.19 ^{ab}	2.71 ± 0.32 ^a	1.21 ± 0.09 ^b	1.59 ± 0.15 ^a	101.49 ± 16.77 ^a	15.01 ± 2.72 ^a	16.80 ± 3.45 ^{ab}	70.51 ± 18.16 ^a	1.14 ± 0.14 ^a	13.06 ± 0.52 ^a	4.35 ± 0.55 ^a
	NFT	2.36 ± 0.69 ^a	1.05 ± 0.17 ^a	2.92 ± 0.02 ^a	1.10 ± 0.17 ^b	1.63 ± 0.02 ^a	102.57 ± 9.56 ^a	14.96 ± 1.54 ^a	15.29 ± 0.94 ^b	66.22 ± 2.98 ^a	1.52 ± 0.22 ^a	13.15 ± 0.12 ^a	3.64 ± 0.61 ^a
	MB	1.66 ± 0.29 ^a	0.78 ± 0.13 ^b	2.91 ± 0.10 ^a	1.28 ± 0.13 ^b	1.66 ± 0.07 ^a	118.90 ± 7.30 ^a	14.48 ± 3.41 ^a	17.45 ± 1.99 ^{ab}	59.95 ± 8.07 ^a	1.27 ± 0.34 ^a	11.40 ± 3.53 ^a	3.48 ± 0.74 ^a
	SP	2.09 ± 0.76 ^a	0.83 ± 0.05 ^{ab}	2.94 ± 0.15 ^a	1.75 ± 0.05 ^a	1.60 ± 0.25 ^a	121.12 ± 2.43 ^a	11.48 ± 2.69 ^a	19.68 ± 0.59 ^a	63.27 ± 5.30 ^a	1.49 ± 0.17 ^a	13.09 ± 1.67 ^a	3.75 ± 0.24 ^a
T1.2	DWC	2.33 ± 0.44 ^a	0.73 ± 0.05 ^a	1.95 ± 0.24 ^b	1.11 ± 0.05 ^a	1.02 ± 0.06 ^b	254.90 ± 79.62 ^c	6.24 ± 1.17 ^a	14.17 ± 2.61 ^a	77.83 ± 22.81 ^a	1.41 ± 0.35 ^a	12.68 ± 0.50 ^a	3.45 ± 0.49 ^a
	NFT	2.38 ± 0.34 ^a	0.71 ± 0.20 ^a	1.34 ± 0.27 ^c	0.96 ± 0.20 ^a	0.98 ± 0.03 ^b	189.41 ± 43.31 ^d	8.17 ± 3.11 ^a	16.02 ± 0.29 ^a	65.67 ± 18.44 ^a	1.51 ± 0.10 ^a	13.33 ± 0.97 ^a	3.77 ± 0.71 ^a
	MB	2.47 ± 0.36 ^a	0.63 ± 0.02 ^a	1.95 ± 0.56 ^b	0.87 ± 0.02 ^a	1.36 ± 0.22 ^a	414.60 ± 41.15 ^a	7.68 ± 1.53 ^a	14.99 ± 1.83 ^a	67.32 ± 19.72 ^a	1.57 ± 0.16 ^a	13.30 ± 1.58 ^a	3.68 ± 0.44 ^a
	SP	2.17 ± 0.21 ^a	0.66 ± 0.15 ^a	2.45 ± 0.19 ^a	0.93 ± 0.15 ^a	1.47 ± 0.09 ^a	337.42 ± 24.31 ^b	8.21 ± 3.01 ^a	15.08 ± 2.99 ^a	64.14 ± 78.10 ^a	1.49 ± 0.13 ^a	13.43 ± 1.42 ^a	3.12 ± 0.31 ^a

Data are expressed as means ± standard error (SE). Lower case letters indicate significant differences after least significant difference (LSD) post hoc test (significance level $p < 0.05$ and $p < 0.01$, not significantly at $p \geq 0.05$) for each parameter. Different upper superscript letters within cultivation systems indicate a significant difference at $p < 0.05$ and $p < 0.01$, not significantly at $p \geq 0.05$ (LSD test). CS: cultivation systems: DWC: Deep water culture, NFT: Nutrient Film Technique, MB: Media- bed system, SP: Sandponic.

As for the chlorophyll content, chlorophyll A content was similar in all subsystems and planting spacing treatments. The highest chlorophyll B and Carotene contents were observed in the lettuces from the DWC subsystem with narrow planting spacing, while the lowest chlorophyll B and carotene were measured in the MB subsystem with larger planting spacing (Fig. 2).

3.3 Taste tests

In hydroponically grown Batavia lettuces, the overall consumer acceptability was higher for lettuces from the DWC and NFT subsystems (there was no significant difference between each other), whereas overall acceptability for Sandponic lettuces was rated very negatively compared to other lettuces (Table 4). Regarding the appearance and aftertaste ratings by testers, lettuces from the DWC and NFT were rated with the highest scores. The lettuces from Sandponic were rated the lowest scores for appearance and aftertaste, while the lettuces grown in the Media-bed system received moderate ratings. Lettuces from DWC and NFT systems were less bitter, they were sweeter, and of a better overall flavour compared to plants grown in MB and SP. Moreover, DWC and NFT plants had a more likeable aftertaste, colour and more likeable crunchiness compared with plants grown in MB and SP. The smell of lettuces grown in SP was more neutral and less fresh than other hydroponically grown lettuces. Among hydroponically grown lettuces, lettuces from DWC and NFT were mostly preferred as 'best lettuce'.

Table 4
Sensory attributes and mean scores of lettuces grown under different cultivation systems

	Lettuce origins	Overall acceptability ¹	Appearance ¹	Overall flavor ¹	Aftertaste ¹	Sweetness ²	Bitterness ²	Color ²	Crunchiness ¹	Smell	Best lettuce
T1 (n = 21) F:8. M:13	DWC	8.76 ^a	8.76 ^a	9.0 ^a	7.38 ^a	4.57 ^a	1.00 ^c	4.57 ^a	8.62 ^a	29.60% fresh	52.4%
	NFT	8.95 ^a	8.90 ^a	9.19 ^a	7.71 ^a	4.67 ^a	1.00 ^c	4.62 ^a	8.48 ^a	29.60% fresh	47%
	MP	6.00 ^b	6.00 ^b	6.04 ^b	5.10 ^b	4.29 ^a	1.57 ^b	3.90 ^b	6.29 ^b	28.20% fresh. 7.1% neutral	-
	SP	4.81 ^c	4.95 ^c	4.38 ^b	3.19 ^c	1.71 ^b	3.86 ^a	3.43 ^b	5.71 ^b	10.60 fresh, 92.9% neutral	-
Sensory attributes of lettuces from hydroponic and soil-based cultivation are assessed independently. Lower case letters within each main treatment indicate significant differences after least significant difference (LSD) post hoc test (significance level $p < 0.05$ and $p < 0.01$, not significantly at $p \geq 0.05$) for each parameter. Smell and best lettuce preference are expressed as a percentage. Cultivation systems: HP: hydroponic subsystems, SBC: soil – based cultivation. Lettuce origins: DWC: Deep water culture, NFT: Nutrient Film Technique, MB: Media- bed system, SP: Sandponic, SC: Soil-based cultivation, LM: lettuces purchased from local market. Trials: T1: Trial 1, T2: Trial 2. N: number of testers, gender of testers: F: female, M: male.											
¹ Evaluated with a 10-point scale: 1 = dislike extremely; 10 = like extremely.											
² Evaluated with a 5-point scale: 1 = not at all bitter or sweet; 5 = extremely bitter or sweet											

4 Discussion

Our study documents how planting spacing can affect lettuce growth parameters, plant nutrient uptake and sensory attributes of lettuces grown under different growing systems. In terms of lettuce growth, our findings confirm the hypothesis that the yield of lettuces per unit area increases, while the yield per plant decreases with increasing plant density in DWC and NFT set-ups. In addition, our results provide evidence that the interaction between the cultivation method and shoot height is an important key factor for obtaining a higher yield in hydroponic cultivation. The higher yield per plant in DWC and NFT are obtained as compared to other hydroponic systems in larger planting spacing. In addition to this, the final shoot heights of lettuces grown in the DWC subsystem with narrow planting spacing were significantly higher than in other cultivation methods. The greater accumulation of biomass observed in lettuces cultivated in these hydroponic subsystems is directly associated with the availability of nutrients in the nutrient solution, as well as lower water stress⁵.

As for the number of leaves, which is one of the most important factors affecting plant yield, DWC and NFT systems outperformed the other systems in both treatments. Contrary to our results, a recent study demonstrated that the number of leaves and yield were significantly higher in lettuces grown in DWC than in NFT and soil-based cultivation in two different crop cycles cultivated under different growing seasons³⁹. Differences in terms of the number of leaves per plant may be associated with the nutrient solution composition, especially N and its uptake by plants⁴⁰⁻⁴². However, there was no significant difference in N uptake among hydroponic cultivation systems.

The root length provides a larger surface area for nutrient uptake, which promotes plant growth⁴³. Our results show that the lettuce root length in DWC was nearly three-fold longer than the root length in the SP. The poor root development in the media system with sand may have occurred due to lower dissolved oxygen compared to other cultivation methods^{44,45}.

In addition, the formation of root hairs depends on both genetics and nutrient uptake, particularly the uptake of phosphate and nitrate. In the present study, a higher P level was observed in lettuces from the NFT system. A previous study indicated that the root length and number are negatively correlated with P concentration in rape, spinach and tomato when the P supply is improved. Even though the higher root density increases P uptake⁴⁶. In many culture plants, N uptake increases the biomass. However, previous studies indicated that an increase in the rate of N supply did not increase the yield of leafy vegetables such as lettuce, spinach and baby leaf lettuce⁴⁷⁻⁴⁹. In our study, the higher root weight in lettuces from NFT systems with narrow planting spacing did not increase at the same rate of shoot fresh mass. The greater root growth may not lead to greater shoot growth all the time due to the limited availability of nutrients and water⁵⁰. If it is ensured that each nutrient that the plant needs in the growing systems is in direct contact with the root surfaces in a constant concentration at constant frequent fertigation, this will not be a limiting factor⁵¹.

In addition to the environmental factors mentioned above, the underlying reasons for the lowest vegetative plant development in media-bed systems with sand and gravel may be associated with the increased EC and pH value of nutrient solution tanks. In our study, the pH of the nutrition solution was adjusted and maintained at the preferred range of 5.4 to 6.0, which allows for maximum availability of nutrients to plant roots. Previous studies have shown that even slight increases of pH to levels of 7.0 could significantly reduce lettuce fresh and dry mass⁵². Even though the EC-value is maintained within a range of 1.5 -2.0 dS/cm for optimal lettuce growth, the fluctuations in EC value may negatively affect the nutrient uptake by plants. Previous studies showed that optimal EC value may vary depending on measured growth or leaf content parameters. In a study, the higher growth parameters were obtained from the Batavia cultivar of lettuce and basil at EC of 0.9 and 1.2 dS/m, whereas the higher nitrate accumulation and chlorophyll content were measured at EC value of 2 dS/m for both lettuce and basil⁵³. In another study of Kappel et al. (2021)⁵⁴ it has been observed that the higher EC value can increase the nitrate level and

chlorophyll content with less yield in some varieties of lettuce as well. In the present study, the existence of algae was observed in the media-bed grow units with sand (SP) and gravel (MB). The algal development was higher in the SP subsystem than in MB grow-beds. Even though black plastic covers were used to prevent algal development, these growth beds were infected with algae. This algal development may reduce plant growth parameters since these organisms can compete for nutrients and produce toxins that might inhibit or stop plant growth. In addition to this, algae can lead to clogging in the irrigation systems of grow beds⁵⁵.

While planting spacing predominantly influenced the content of lettuce chlorophylls and carotene content, all production variables in the present study affected the nutrient uptake and concentration of leaf nutrient content. Higher planting density can reduce photosynthetic capacity, as the necessary light cannot be provided enough to the plant for photosynthesis⁵⁶. Our data seem to support these interpretations. On the other hand, previous studies indicated that higher chlorophyll concentrations can be associated with higher N content. Nitrogen (N) is vital for photosynthesis and plays a great role in yield. However, the yield and N contents in lettuce leaves did not exhibit a linear relationship with chlorophyll content, since plant growth and yield are not only dependent on chlorophyll content⁴². In the current study, the lettuces grown from the DWC hydroponic system showed more chlorophyll and carotene content compared to other cultivation methods in the narrow planting spacing.

The uptake of plant essential nutrient elements can vary depending on the pH value of the nutrient solution. A slightly acidic pH value (5.5–6.5) is optimum for hydroponically grown leafy vegetables because iron (Fe), manganese (Mn), boron (B), copper and zinc (Zn) are absorbable by plants at pH values below 6. However, pH values 6–8 are optimum for the uptake of macro elements such as phosphorus (P), potassium (K), magnesium (Mg), calcium (Ca) and sulfur (S)^{57–59}. Some scientists suggest that the pH value of nutrient solution should be maintained at a range of 5.5–6.0^{58,60}. Our results confirm that the lettuces grown with a pH value below 6 showed higher plant growth parameters in DWC and NFT than in other cultivation systems. The quantitative relationship between the individual elements, as well as the ionic form, may be as significant as the concentration of each element in optimizing the nutritional status of the plant³⁰. According to Liebig's minimum law, the maximum growth rate is determined by the least available nutrient⁶¹. Moreover, the concentration of certain ions can support or inhibit the uptake of other ions. The connected ions have a synergistic or antagonistic relationship. The increase of Mg and N levels can enter into competition with the uptake of potassium⁶². Our results revealed that higher Mg content in lettuces from the MB with larger spacing decreased the potassium (K) level.

Consumers' taste, smell, appearance and color preference for lettuce are the most important aspects of marketable fresh consumed vegetables. However, few studies have investigated the sensory evaluation of lettuces grown in different cultivation systems under several cropping seasons. Our present study shows that lettuces grown in DWC and NFT sub-systems have higher sensory attributes compared to other hydroponic systems. Contrary to this, a study from Baba and Ikeguchi (2015)⁶³ indicated that the sand used in the Sandponic system as substrate can increase the taste of crops such as tomato, as moisture in the sand is less absorbed by the plants compared to other substrates and plants have better taste due to the condensed flavours through less water in the crop.

Consumers tend to prefer the crunchy texture of the lettuce and associate this crunchiness with freshness and wholesomeness⁶⁴. Simonne et al. (2001)⁶⁵ observed that although the N source did not affect lettuce yield, they recommended using calcium nitrate to enhance lettuce crunchiness. In our case, we observed that Calcium (Ca) content as the main effect was higher in lettuces grown in MB and SP. Moreover, fresh smell and crunchiness features are positively correlated with consumer perception of the preference for "best lettuce".

The lettuces grown in MB and SP cultivation were rated as having a bitter taste. Bitterness can be associated with the uptake of nitrogen, and the available P affects the flavour of taste^{62,65}. However, the current study showed no significant difference in N content. In our case, nutrient contents of lettuces grown in different cultivation systems were generally within ranges but these ranges are quite wide and there are considerable differences. Furthermore, previous researchers demonstrated that the bitterness can increase at higher temperatures and may be related to secondary metabolites such as phenolic content, as our experimental lettuces were grown at warm conditions^{66–69}.

5 Conclusions

The present study compared the lettuce growth and biomass in different sub-systems of hydroponics. In detail, the effects of different subsystems and planting densities on vegetative growth, sensory attributes of lettuces and nutrient uptake by lettuce grown in a closed soilless system were investigated. Our findings indicated that the yield per unit area increased with the increase in plant density, whereas the biomass of lettuce decreased in narrow spacing. We observed that lettuces from the DWC and NFT subsystems at both planting spacings had higher vegetative plant growth parameters such as shoot height, number of leaves, and root length. Furthermore, sensory attributes (appearance, taste of lettuces and colour etc.) of lettuce were found higher in DWC and NFT subsystems than in other systems. The most preferred lettuce rates were 52.4% and 47.6% in DWC and NFT, respectively. The highest chlorophyll B and carotene, which are essential pigments of higher plant assimilatory tissues, were measured to interpret biochemical and structural results obtained on lettuce tissues. The highest chlorophyll B and carotene values were measured in fresh lettuces grown in the DWC with higher plant density.

In conclusion, many studies documented that hydroponic systems have great potential for crop production compared to conventional agriculture. In contrast, a few studies tested the different hydroponic subsystems and planting spacing. The present study provides direct evidence that the DWC and NFT subsystems performed the best, i.e. produced more yield and higher plant growth parameters. Additional to this, lettuce grown in the DWC system had higher chlorophyll B, and carotene content in narrow planting spacing, and were the most preferred lettuces compared to other cultivation systems.

Declarations

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Author's Contributions D.Ç., R.L., Mo.H., H. El- G., Ma.H. conceived and designed the experiments; H.E. G. performed the experiments; D.Ç. analyzed the data; D.Ç. wrote the first version of the manuscript. All authors commented on previous versions of the manuscript. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

Competing interests

The authors declare no competing interests.

Ethical approval. We confirm that all methods were performed in accordance with the relevant guidelines and regulations by including a statement in the Methods section to this effect. Experimental research on plants, including the collection of plant material, agrees with relevant institutional, national, and international guidelines and legislation.

Data availability

The datasets generated and/or analyzed during the current study are available from the corresponding author on reasonable request.

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Figures

Figure 1

The experimental design used to assess the lettuce growth in various hydroponic sub-systems and soil-based cultivation. These systems: (A)- DWC: Deep Water Culture, (B)- NFT: Nutrient Film Technique, (C)- MB: Media- Bed system and (D)- SP: Sandponics

Figure 2
 Chlorophyll and carotene contents, and dry mass of lettuces grown under different planting spacing and cultivation methods. (A) chlorophyll a, (B) chlorophyll b, and (C) carotene content. Means with a different letter within each treatment and cultivation methods are significantly different by the LSD test at $p < 0.05$. DWC: Deep water culture, NFT: Nutrient Film Technique, MB: Media- bed system, SP: Sandponic, SC: Soil-based cultivation. Narrow planting spacing (20*25 cm or 30*35 cm for soil cultivation, larger planting spacings (24*25cm or 35*45 cm for soil cultivation).